

BRIDGE-BS

Blue Growth Incubators | Service Dynamics | Empowered Citizens

D9.4 Mapping past and ongoing Ocean Literacy initiatives in the Black Sea & developing the Black Sea Literacy Network

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000240

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 9.4: ‘mapping past and ongoing Ocean Literacy initiatives in the Black Sea & developing the Black Sea Literacy (BSL) Network’, describes the progress on the road towards establishing, for the first time, a lasting and meaningful Black Sea Literacy Network. As a starting point for building the BSL Network, the European Marine Science Educators Association (EMSEA) has conducted an online survey during April 2022 to inventorize ongoing and recent Ocean Literacy (OL) activities from 2012 and beyond. The identified OL initiatives were uploaded to an Online Directory in the BRIDGE-BS website. EMSEA invited all the stakeholders involved in the identified OL activities on an annual EMSEA conference in Batumi, Georgia in October 2023. This conference was dedicated to Black Sea Literacy and marked the official establishment of the BSL Network. EMSEA will continue updating the Online Directory as a result of upcoming additional rounds of surveys. Additionally, EMSEA will periodically organize and engage in small meetings/open days in Black Sea countries to reach out to the relevant stakeholders to foster networking and collaborations in the Black Sea Basin.

D9.4 was initially planned as a “Database of OL initiatives in the Black Sea”. However, in the BRIDGE-BS 2023 Amendment, the name of the deliverable is changed to “D9.4 Mapping past and ongoing Ocean Literacy initiatives in the Black Sea & developing the Black Sea Literacy Network” to reflect the progress that has been made to establish the BSL.

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1. Introduction

BRIDGE-BS establishes an Ocean Literacy (OL) Network for the first time in the Black Sea Basin (BSB) to develop ownership and stewardship for the protection of the Black Sea. The aim of the Network is to bring together marine scientists, educators, ocean professionals and anyone who is enthusiastic and curious about the Black Sea nature.

The OL concept was introduced in Europe a decade ago. However, many organizations and individuals in the Black Sea countries have a longer history of teaching about their seas and engaging communities. Information about such teaching and engagement activities, which we collectively refer to as the Ocean Literacy Initiatives, is sporadic and hardly obtainable because it has never been inventoried in a consistent manner. Examples of OL Initiatives are fieldtrips to coastal reserves, citizen science activities, competitions for youngsters, school projects, teacher workshops, species poster exhibitions, information portals, science class protocols, beach cleaning trips and any education and/or outreach activities related to the Black Sea. The lack of information on Ocean Literacy Initiatives in the Black Sea Basin precludes effective collaboration and sharing of best practices among educators.

The roadmap for the Black Sea Literacy (BSL) Network highlights the milestones and deliverables of the journey in establishing a comprehensive and lasting multi-stakeholder network (Figure 1). The roadmap consists of concrete steps from April 2022 to January 2025 including the survey and inventory of BSL initiatives, the creation of an online directory integrated into the BRIDGE-BS website, the organisation of the EMSEA conference to bring the BSL network together and the future steps that are necessary to grow the network and keep it running.

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Figure 1. The road towards establishing and implementing the Black Sea Literacy Network

1.1 Inventory

The European Marine Science Educators Association (EMSEA) conducted an online survey in April 2022 to inventorize ongoing and recent Ocean Literacy (OL) activities, started from 2012 and beyond. Initially, the partner organizations and beneficiaries of the BRIDGE-BS project were approached and asked to submit those projects and initiatives that they were part of and that involved elements of OL. As part of the questionnaire (available on line here), participants were asked to nominate persons or organisations from their professional networks, outside of the BRIDGE-BS project, who would be relevant to partake in the survey. The nominated organisations were then invited to participate in the survey. The invitation to participate in the survey was also placed on the BRIDGE-BS website and social media channels.

This activity, resulted in 71 entries on recent OL projects and initiatives in the Black Sea region. All the entries were carefully revisited to identify their relevance; the rounds of revisions shortlisted to 33 relevant BSL projects and/or initiatives. These 33 entries were categorized according to the type of activity and grouped into 8 categories: outreach; competition; training activities; field trips; science education; beach cleanup; summer school and citizen science (Figure 2). Often, the entries were characterized by more than one category, in which case multiple categories were ascribed to

them for the ease of online findability. These results were used to generate an online directory of Black Sea OL activities.

Figure 2. Types of identified Black Sea Literacy activities

‘Outreach’ was the predominant Ocean Literacy activity in the identified BSL projects and/or initiatives followed by ‘Science education’, ‘Training activities’, ‘Beach cleanup’, ‘Citizen science’, ‘Competition’, ‘Field trips’ and ‘Summer school’.

Under the theme ‘Outreach’ most of the activities were centred around passing on the information, e.g. via publishing the findings of scientific projects on the Black Sea on the project website or presenting the results at conferences and other forums, without engaging the target audiences into any joint activity. Similarly, ‘Science education’, the second most prevailing Ocean Literacy activity of all identified projects, involved educating elementary, middle and high school students as well as university students on the findings of the projects, but without joint actions.

As Ocean Literacy is more than awareness raising and education and involves components such as activism, behavioural change and emotional connection amongst others (McKinley et al. 2023), it is important to raise the significance of more hands-on, comprehensive Ocean Literacy activities in the agenda of the identified BSL network.

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The development of an online directory of recent Black Sea Literacy initiatives, activities and good practices is the first step towards establishing the Black Sea Literacy network. The directory provides necessary insights into the current landscape of OL activities in the Black Sea basin and helps with the identification of relevant stakeholders. Furthermore, the online directory helps identify gaps in current OL activities and the opportunities for involving stakeholders in OL initiatives.

EMSEA is looking and will keep researching the new and ongoing Ocean Literacy (OL) projects and initiatives to keep the OL online directory up to date and as comprehensive as possible.

2. Establish an Ocean Literacy Network

2.1 EMSEA Conference in Batumi, Georgia

The European Marine Science Educators Association (EMSEA) organized a conference to bring the stakeholders engaged in the Black Sea Literacy together. The EMSEA conference was held in the Black Sea region, in Batumi, Georgia from October 16th to 18th. EMSEA organizes conferences regularly on an annual basis, which usually focus on small attendance, but big impact and Batumi was no exception. For annual conferences, small to medium venues are chosen to ensure that everyone gets the chance to meet each other.

In 2023 EMSEA dedicated its annual conference to the Black Sea Literacy. Batumi (Georgia) was chosen as the venue as a city directly next to the Black Sea. The conference was organized in a hybrid mode to allow participation from a broader audience.

The conference brought together 50 participants, both in person and online, representing 12 different nationalities including students from two Georgian universities: 1) Tbilisi State University and 2) Batumi State University. Other than students, among the participants were marine scientists, educators involved in education on the Black Sea, companies involved in the blue economy and ocean professionals. (Figure 3)

Figure 3. EMSEA Conference dedicated to the Black Sea, 16-18 October 2023, Batumi Georgia¹

The conference was organized around the 4 main themes (see for details the Agenda under Annex I):

- 1) Ocean literacy in the Black Sea
- 2) Blue economy and education
- 3) Water sports and ocean literacy;
- 4) Ocean conservation

These themes were selected as they represent the domains of Ocean Literacy, which EMSEA is actively involved in. Additionally, Theme 1 and 2 were also recurring as themes in the living labs that took place under WP6 as a common need in the region. If some elements were not covered with these themes, the stakeholders had an opportunity to contribute and present related issues under the Open Session. At the beginning of the program, a welcome session took place to set the scene with the inclusion of officials from the European Commission, the H2020-funded DOORS project and the Common Maritime Agenda for the Black Sea's National Hub for Georgia. (Annex 1)

In total 23 abstracts were selected for oral/poster presentations and workshops. On the second day of the conference, EMSEA organized the Black Sea Literacy workshop where participants were divided into groups of 6 so that each group had a mixture of different experiences and backgrounds, and each group was given a set of questions for brainstorming on how Black Sea Literacy network can grow and effectively bring ocean literacy to Black Sea citizens.

¹ <https://bridgeblacksea.org/index.php/2023/10/20/emsea-annual-conference-2023-was-held-in-batumi-georgia/>

2.1.1. Results of the workshop at the EMSEA Conference

The workshop was organized in person around 4 round tables with one facilitator of the discussions and a note taker on each table. In total 24 participants were present in person who participated in the workshop. Each table was tasked to discuss the questions and present the answers and solutions at the end of the workshop.

Based on the analysis of the notes from each table we developed the themes (“recurrent unifying concepts or statements about the content/subject of the inquiry”) for 2 questions:

- 1) What does Ocean Literacy mean to you? and
- 2) What are your expectations from this network?

The established themes were then counted and plotted to determine their relative importance based on the frequency of mentioning (Figures 4 and 5)

For the meaning of the OL, 12 themes were identified that were mentioned 33 times in total (Figure 4). Some themes were mentioned only once, while others more than once. The theme that was most frequently mentioned around the meaning of the OL was the ‘Holistic, cross-sectoral understanding of the Ocean’, which together with the theme that OL means ‘Everything: lifestyle’ displays the grand importance of OL in the Black Sea and beyond (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The themes of the meaning of the Ocean Literacy to the Black Sea Literacy Network

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As for the question on the network expectations from establishing the BSL Network, using the workshop notes, 7 themes were established, mentioned 30 times in total (Figure 5). The most frequently mentioned theme was “Leveraging OL efforts”. This theme is about the increased visibility and advocating capacity of the network vs. Individual OL practitioners to push the OL high in the education and political agenda.

Additionally, the BSL network is expected to serve as a knowledge hub and a platform for cross-country collaborations.

Figure 5. Themes of BSL Network expectations from the Black Sea Literacy Network

3. Next Steps for Black Sea Literacy Network

Establishing the Black Sea Literacy network will entail a series of meetings with identified stakeholders who will be contributing to the network. EMSEA is organizing a follow-up online workshop in July 2024 to bring the network together, including those who were present in Batumi and continue building up on the outcomes of the Batumi conference (see Figure 1 for the timeline). The goals of this workshop are:

- i) to present to the network the roadmap of BSL (Figure 1), as well as the findings of the workshop held in Batumi (Figures 4 and 5);

- ii) ii) to discuss with the network the way forward especially on how to meet the expectations that were established during the workshop at the EMSEA conference (Figure 5) and
- iii) iii) to train the extended BSL Network, including those members who were absent in Batumi, on OL principles and real-world applications in order to guide, inspire and increase the impact of the network.

Additionally, EMSEA has already planned to periodically organize and engage in small meetings/open days in Black Sea countries with the aim to reach out to the relevant stakeholders and to foster networking and collaborations in the Black Sea Basin (see Figure 1 for activities).

References

McKinley E, Burdon D, Shellock R. 2023. The evolution of ocean literacy: A new framework for the United Nations Ocean Decade and beyond. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 186:114467

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ANNEX I. EMSEA Conference Agenda

EMSEA Conference 16th – 18th October 2023 BLUE EDUCATION and BLUE ECONOMY in the BLACK SEA

Monday 16 October

09:30 – 10.00 Conference registration

10.00 – 11.00 Welcome session

Nicola Bridge, president European Marine Science Educators Association

Wendy Bonne, policy officer European Commission (virtual)

Pinar Uygurer, Project manager BRIDGE-BS, Middle East Technical University, Turkey

Dina Eparkhina., EUROGOOS, DOORS (virtual)

Mamuka Berdzenishvili, Executive Director Tourism Institute

11.00 – 11.30 Coffee break

11.30 – 13.00 Presentations: Ocean literacy in the Black Sea

BLACK SEA LITERACY NETWORK

Aleksander Gogaladze, EMSEA

YOUTH ENGAGEMENT IN OCEAN LITERACY: HOW THE BLACK SEA YOUNG AMBASSADORS SUPPORT OCEAN LITERACY IN THE BLACK SEA AND EUROPE

Ezgi Sahin Yucel, METU Institute of Marine Sciences, Turkey

Marika Makharadze, Bridge Black Sea Young Ambassador

SCIENCE COMMUNICATION IN PRACTICE: SHOWCASING THE PATHWAYS FOR BRIDGING THE GAPS BETWEEN SCIENCE AND SOCIETY WITHIN THE EU H2020 BRIDGE-BS PROJECT

Özgün Evrim Sayilkan, METU Institute of Marine Sciences, Turkey

OUTCOMES OF THE OCEAN LITERACY COURSES IN TÜRKİYE

Elif Özgür, Turkish Marine Research Foundation

TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN UKRAINE DURING THE FULL-SCALE INVASION OF RUSSIA

Liubov Savinykh-Paltseva, UkrSCES, Ukraine (virtual)

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NETWORK OF EUROPEAN BLUE SCHOOLS IN THE BLACK SEA

Evy Copejans, Managing director EMSEA

Khatuna Khachapuridze, Blue School Georgia

13.00 – 15.00 Lunch and Poster presentations

15.00 – 16.30 Presentations Blue Economy and Education

IS THE MARITIME PROFESSION STILL ATTRACTIVE? THE CASE OF GREECE

Dimitris Gavalas, National & Kapodistrian University of Athens

THE ROLE OF EDUCATION FOR THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF FISHERIES AND AQUACULTURE WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF THE BLUE ECONOMY

Maia Chkhobadze, Department of Environmental Supervision head of Biodiversity Control Service Ministry of Environment Protection and Agriculture of Georgia

MSc PROGRAM IN SUSTAINABILITY & QUALITY IN MARINE INDUSTRY

Fani Sakellariadou, University of Piraeus, Dept of Maritime Studies, Greece (virtual)

Presentations: conservation

SUSTAINABILITY IS AT STAKE: ENGAGING THE NEXT GENERATION IN OCEAN CONSERVATION AND THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

Teresa Santos, Oceanário de Lisboa, Portugal

EDUCATION AND ENGAGEMENT FOR CROSS-BORDER MARINE PROTECTED AREAS

Anuschka Miller, Scottish Association for Marine Science, UK

16.30 – 17.00 Closing remarks of the day

17.30 – 19.00 Reception

Tuesday 17 October

09:30 – 10.00 DIGITAL TOOLS FOR EDUCATION ON BLUE ECONOMY

Prof. ir. Eden Mamut, Black Sea Universities Network BSUN, Romania

10.00 – 11.30 Presentations: Open session

PROBLEU: PROMOTING OCEAN AND WATER LITERACY IN SCHOOL COMMUNITIES

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Luigi Ceccaroni, Eathwatch, UK

CITIZEN SCIENCE OBSERVATORIES AS A BLENDED LEARNING ENVIRONMENT
CODESIGNED UNDER THE UMBRELLA OF BLUE SCHOOLS: THE CASE OF MINKA
PLATFORM

Elisabet Bonfill Molina, Institut de Ciències del Mar, Spain

ESCAPE ROOM

Binke D’Haese, Flanders Marine Institute, Belgium

WHALETALK

Mia Leng, Scottish Association for Marine Science, UK

11.00 – 11.45 Coffee break

11.45 – 12.45 Workshop

DEVELOPING AN OCEAN STEM CENTRE

Anuschka Miller, Scottish Association for Marine Science, UK

12.45 – 13.45 Lunch

13.45 – 15.15 Presentations: Open session

THE BALTIC SEA NATURALLY

Dominika Wiśniewska, National Marine Fisheries Research Institute, Gdynia
Aquarium Education Center

CONNECTING CITIZEN OBSERVATORY NETWORKS WITH BLUE SCHOOLS
THROUGH THE OPEN SCHOOLING FRAMEWORK: THE EXAMPLE OF ANERIS
PROJECT

Berta Companys, Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM-CSIC), Spain

Presentations: Watersports

“A DIP IN THE SEA” – A DIVING AND OCEAN LITERACY PROGRAMME
AVAILABLE FOR EVERYONE

Diogo Geraldes, Oceanário de Lisboa, Portugal

POSIDONIA ESCAPE EXPERIENCE: THE FIRST UNDERWATER ESCAPE ROOM IN
THE MEDITERRANEAN SEA TO EDUCATE ABOUT POSIDONIA MEADOWS

Elisabet Bonfill Molina, Plàncton, Divulgació i Serveis Marins, Spain

CURRENT DEVELOPMENTS IN THE YACHTING INDUSTRY AND THE BLUE
CRUISE CHALLENGES IN BODRUM

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Aziz Muslu, Samsun University, Turkey

OCEAN SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH EDUCATION AND SPORT

Dominika Wojcieszek, European Marine Science Educators Association, Poland

15.15 – 15.45 Coffee break

15.45 – 17.45 Workshop

BLACK SEA LITERACY WORKSHOP

19.00 – 21.00 Conclusion of the Conference and Networking

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